

Supplementary material for the publication:

The effect of light directionality on alertness and cognitive performance during post-lunch dip

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All the data presented in this document forms supplementary material for the analysis of results from an experiment performed by Nikodem Derengowski for the LightCap project at the Technische Universität Berlin. This document includes complete datasets to be used for a series of publications.

The documents consist of the following:

- Section A: Models description and variables overview
- Section B: Results of the fitting of models
- Section C: Random effects of the fitted models

Section A1 – Models description for multivariate models 1,4,5 (table A1.1)

The general form of regression models was specified with the formulas (A.1) - (A.3):

$$Y_{ij} \sim N(\mu_{ij}, \sigma_\epsilon), (A.1)$$

$$\mu_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot LightScene_{ij} + \beta_2 \cdot TestBlock_{ij} + \beta_3 \cdot LightScene_{ij} \times TestBlock_{ij} + u_{0i}, (A.2)$$

$$u_{0i} \sim N(0, \sigma_0), (A.3)$$

whereby: the outcome variable Y_{ij} was modeled as normally distributed with a mean of μ_{ij} and a standard deviation σ_ϵ and varies between i subjects and j *TestBlock* categories; β_0 - is the population mean (the model constant) for the *LightScene* and *TestBlock* reference categories (baseline); β_1 - is the difference between the reference category and the other categories for the *TestBlock* reference category, compared to the *LightScene* reference category; β_2 - is the change over time for the *LightScene* reference category; β_3 - is the *LightScene*-by-*TestBlock* interaction (target effect). In addition, the model accounts for subject-level variation around the baseline grand mean over the term u_{0i} , which was modelled as normally distributed with a mean of zero and a standard deviation σ_0 .

For the other models (except for model 2 and model 3), the formulas A.1 and A.2 change to (A.4) and (A.5):

$$Y_i \sim N(\mu_i, \sigma_\varepsilon), (A.4)$$

$$\mu_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Predictor}_i + u_{0i}, (A.5)$$

Models 2 and 3 were not reported as they could not be fitted.

Table A1.1 List of the fitted LMM models and their general characteristics.

Model type	Model name	Dependent / response Variable	Explanatory Variables	
Multivariate (cognitive performance and sleepiness)	model1	GoNoGo Reaction Speed	LightScene, TestBlock	
	model2 ¹	GoNoGo Correct Response		
	model3 ¹	Nback Correct Response		
	model4	PVT Reaction Speed		
	model5	KSS		
Univariate – (mood scales)	model6	MDFB GS Scale	LightScene	
	model7	MDFB WM Scale		
	model8	MDFB RU Scale		
Univariate – Visual Comfort scales	model9	Pleasantness	LightScene	
	model10	Brightness		
	model11	Glare		
	model12	Perceived colour temperature		
Univariate – Room Comfort scales	model13	Headache	LightScene	
	model14	Perceived room air quality		
	model15	Perceived room humidity		
	model16	Perceived room smell		
Univariate – covariates	model17	KSS Score	PSQI Score	
	Model18		Food Factor	
	model19		CO2 level ⁴	
	model20		Humidity level in %	
	model21		Room temp in °C	
	model22		Light history: LED ²	
	model23		Light history: Indoor DL ²	
	model24		Light history: time outside ⁴	
	model25		GoNoGo Reaction Speed	PSQI Score
	model26			Food Factor
	model27			CO2 level ⁴
	model28			Humidity level in %
	model29	Room temp in °C		
	model30	Light history: LED ²		
	model31	Light history: Indoor DL ²		
	model32	Light history: time outside ⁴		
	model33	PVT Reaction Speed		PSQI Score
	model34			Food Factor
	model35			CO2 level ⁴
	model36			Humidity level in %
	model37		Room temp in °C	
	model38		Light history: LED ²	
	model39		Light history: Indoor DL ²	
	model40		Light history: time outside ⁴	

Notes: ¹Model not fitted – data singularity. ²Counted in hours in the 24hr period prior to the session, ³Counted in hours on the session day, ⁴Counted as ppm x 10

Table A1.2 Variables overview and descriptive statistics in multivariate models.

Variable	Type	TestBlock	Distribution (mean $\pm$ SD)	Response range	N observations
KSS	N	T0	3.38 $\pm$ 1.32	1-8	198
	N	T1	4.21 $\pm$ 1.65	1-8	198
	N	T2	4.55 $\pm$ 1.84	1-9	198
	N	T3	4.74 $\pm$ 1.89	1-9	198
	N	T4	4.96 $\pm$ 1.86	1-9	198
PVT	Q +	T1	4.21 $\pm$ 0.68	2.23 - 5.70	198
Reaction	Q +	T2	3.90 $\pm$ 0.74	1.89 - 5.38	198
Speed	Q +	T3	3.68 $\pm$ 0.77	1.60 - 5.22	198
GnG	Q +	T1	2.82 $\pm$ 0.60	1.60 - 4.45	198
Reaction	Q +	T2	2.77 $\pm$ 0.63	1.34 - 4.16	198
Speed	Q +	T3	2.74 $\pm$ 0.68	1.24 - 4.36	198

Table A1.3 Variables overview and descriptive statistics in the univariate models.

Variable	Type	Distribution (mean $\pm$ SD)	Response range	N observations
MDFB GS scale	Z	-4.25 $\pm$ 1.74	-18 - 11	198
MDFB WM scale	Z	-6.28 $\pm$ 6.57	-26 - 13	198
MDFB RU scale	Z	-1.28 $\pm$ 3.69	-12 - 6	198
Pleasantness	N	3.46 $\pm$ 1.55	1 - 7	198
Brightness	N	5.47 $\pm$ 0.97	2 - 7	198
Glare	N	4.81 $\pm$ 1.58	1 - 7	198
Perceived color temp.	N	3.00 $\pm$ 1.58	1 - 7	198
Headache	N	1.58 $\pm$ 1.02	1 - 4	198
Perceived air quality	N	5.71 $\pm$ 1.26	2 - 7	198
Perceived subj. Temp.	N	3.45 $\pm$ 0.96	1 - 6	198
Humidity	N	4.03 $\pm$ 0.55	1 - 6	198
Smell	N	5.14 $\pm$ 1.31	2 - 7	198
Loudness	N	3.11 $\pm$ 1.53	1 - 6	198

Table A1.4 General summary statistics of the collected data for the dependent variable: PVT Reaction Speed task. Data are grouped by levels of the Light Scene category with no distinction on Test Blocks (for detailed EMMs go to Section B of this document).

LightScene	Min	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	SD
LS1	1.98	3.62	4.07	4.00	4.52	5.43	0.72
LS2	2.15	3.56	4.09	3.95	4.43	5.33	0.74
LS3	1.60	3.48	3.98	3.95	4.51	5.70	0.79
LS4	1.89	3.30	3.97	3.87	4.49	5.30	0.80
LS5	1.89	3.44	3.94	3.88	4.41	5.32	0.76

Figure A1.1 Histogram showing the distribution of the collected data of the PVT Reaction Speed

Table A1.5 General summary statistics of the collected data for the dependent variable: GoNoGo Reaction Speed. Data are grouped by levels of the Light Scene category with no distinction on Test Blocks (for detailed EMMs go to Section B of this document).

LightScene	Min	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	SD
LS1	1.48	2.42	2.82	2.80	3.19	4.45	0.65
LS2	1.34	2.38	2.72	2.76	3.18	4.36	0.57
LS3	1.24	2.23	2.67	2.70	3.11	4.19	0.64
LS4	1.47	2.32	2.82	2.83	3.29	4.16	0.67
LS5	1.44	2.32	2.81	2.80	3.29	4.12	0.65

Figure A1.2 Histogram showing the distribution of the collected data of the GoNoGo Reaction Speed variable.

Table A1.6 Summary statistics for the data of the variable: GoNoGo Accuracy. Numbers represent the percentage of correct responses. Data are grouped by levels of the Light Scene category with no distinction on Test Blocks This variable was not fitted in a model due to the singularity effect.

LightScene	Min	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	SD
LS1	69.33	96.00	97.33	96.53	98.67	100.00	4.96
LS2	66.67	96.00	97.33	96.74	98.67	100.00	4.56
LS3	86.67	96.00	97.33	96.94	98.67	100.00	2.66
LS4	61.33	96.00	97.33	96.11	98.67	100.00	5.35
LS5	64.00	94.67	97.33	96.06	98.67	100.00	5.35

Figure A1.3 Histogram showing the distribution of the collected data of the GoNoGo Accuracy variable.

Table A1.7 Summary statistics for the data of the variable: 2Back Accuracy. Numbers represent the percentage of correct responses. Data grouped by levels of the Light Scene category with no distinction on Test Blocks. This variable was not fitted in a model due to the singularity effect.

LightScene	Min	1sr Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	SD
LS1	67.78	91.11	94.44	93.34	97.22	100.00	5.78
LS2	68.33	91.67	94.72	93.49	97.22	100.00	5.41
LS3	66.11	90.56	93.89	93.19	97.22	100.00	5.64
LS4	68.89	93.33	96.11	94.61	97.78	100.00	5.17
LS5	71.11	93.33	95.56	94.77	97.78	100.00	5.24

Figure A1.4 Histogram showing the distribution of the collected data of the 2Back Accuracy variable.

Table A1.8 Summary statistics for the data of the variable: KSS score. Data was collected on a 9-step Likert-type scale. Data are grouped by levels of the Light Scene category with no distinction on Test Blocks (for detailed EMMs go to Section B of this document).

LightScene	Min	1sr Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	SD
LS1	1	3	4	4.34	6	9	1.81
LS2	1	3	4	4.32	5	9	1.67
LS3	1	3	4	4.52	6	9	1.97
LS4	1	3	4	4.43	6	9	1.75
LS5	1	3	4	4.13	5	9	1.78

Figure A1.5 Histogram showing the distribution of the collected data of the KSS score variable.

Section B - Results of fitting the models

B1 - Estimated marginal means and contrast analysis for variables: KSS, Go-NoGo

Reaction Speed, PVT Reaction Speed.

Table B1.1 EMMs of KSS for each TB conditioned on LS, df = 234.87.

LightScene	TB	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	TB 0	3.33	0.27	2.38	4.27
	TB 1	4.42	0.27	3.48	5.37
	TB 2	4.50	0.27	3.55	5.45
	TB 3	4.75	0.27	3.80	5.70
	TB 4	4.82	0.27	3.88	5.77
LS2	TB 0	3.52	0.27	2.58	4.47
	TB 1	4.15	0.27	3.20	5.10
	TB 2	4.55	0.27	3.60	5.50
	TB 3	4.67	0.27	3.73	5.62
	TB 4	5.07	0.27	4.13	6.02
LS3	TB 0	3.25	0.27	2.30	4.20
	TB 1	4.32	0.27	3.38	5.27
	TB 2	4.80	0.27	3.85	5.75
	TB 3	4.92	0.27	3.98	5.87
	TB 4	5.32	0.27	4.38	6.27
LS4	TB 0	3.44	0.28	2.49	4.39
	TB 1	4.11	0.28	3.15	5.06
	TB 2	4.70	0.28	3.74	5.65
	TB 3	4.95	0.28	4.00	5.91
	TB 4	5.08	0.28	4.13	6.04
LS5	TB 0	3.41	0.28	2.46	4.37
	TB 1	4.11	0.28	3.15	5.06
	TB 2	4.26	0.28	3.31	5.21
	TB 3	4.47	0.28	3.51	5.42
	TB 4	4.57	0.28	3.61	5.52

Table B1.2 Results of the contrast analysis of KSS model with estimation of effect sizes, $df = 926$.

LightScene	Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1	TB0 - TB1	-1.10	0.31	-1.94	-0.26	0.003	-0.80
	TB0 - TB2	-1.17	0.31	-2.02	-0.33	0.001	-0.85
	TB0 - TB3	-1.42	0.31	-2.27	-0.58	<0.001	-1.03
	TB0 - TB4	-1.50	0.31	-2.34	-0.66	<0.001	-1.09
	TB1 - TB2	-0.07	0.31	-0.92	0.77	0.999	-0.05
	TB1 - TB3	-0.33	0.31	-1.17	0.52	0.830	-0.24
	TB1 - TB4	-0.40	0.31	-1.24	0.44	0.693	-0.29
	TB2 - TB3	-0.25	0.31	-1.09	0.59	0.927	-0.18
	TB2 - TB4	-0.33	0.31	-1.17	0.52	0.830	-0.24
	TB3 - TB4	-0.07	0.31	-0.92	0.77	0.999	-0.05
LS2	TB0 - TB1	-0.63	0.31	-1.47	0.22	0.253	-0.45
	TB0 - TB2	-1.03	0.31	-1.87	-0.18	0.008	-0.74
	TB0 - TB3	-1.15	0.31	-1.99	-0.31	0.002	-0.83
	TB0 - TB4	-1.55	0.31	-2.39	-0.71	<0.001	-1.12
	TB1 - TB2	-0.40	0.31	-1.24	0.44	0.693	-0.29
	TB1 - TB3	-0.53	0.31	-1.37	0.32	0.432	-0.38
	TB1 - TB4	-0.93	0.31	-1.77	-0.08	0.023	-0.67
	TB2 - TB3	-0.13	0.31	-0.97	0.72	0.994	-0.09
	TB2 - TB4	-0.53	0.31	-1.37	0.32	0.432	-0.38
	TB3 - TB4	-0.40	0.31	-1.24	0.44	0.693	-0.29
LS3	TB0 - TB1	-1.08	0.31	-1.92	-0.23	0.005	-0.78
	TB0 - TB2	-1.55	0.31	-2.39	-0.71	<0.001	-1.12
	TB0 - TB3	-1.68	0.31	-2.52	-0.83	<0.001	-1.22
	TB0 - TB4	-2.08	0.31	-2.92	-1.23	<0.001	-1.51
	TB1 - TB2	-0.48	0.31	-1.32	0.37	0.536	-0.34
	TB1 - TB3	-0.60	0.31	-1.44	0.24	0.293	-0.44
	TB1 - TB4	-1.00	0.31	-1.84	-0.16	0.011	-0.73
	TB2 - TB3	-0.13	0.31	-0.97	0.72	0.994	-0.09
	TB2 - TB4	-0.53	0.31	-1.37	0.32	0.432	-0.38
	TB3 - TB4	-0.40	0.31	-1.24	0.44	0.693	-0.29
LS4	TB0 - TB1	-0.67	0.31	-1.52	0.19	0.206	-0.48
	TB0 - TB2	-1.26	0.31	-2.11	-0.40	0.001	-0.91
	TB0 - TB3	-1.51	0.31	-2.37	-0.66	<0.001	-1.10
	TB0 - TB4	-1.64	0.31	-2.49	-0.79	<0.001	-1.19
	TB1 - TB2	-0.59	0.31	-1.44	0.26	0.324	-0.43
	TB1 - TB3	-0.85	0.31	-1.70	0.01	0.053	-0.61
	TB1 - TB4	-0.97	0.31	-1.83	-0.12	0.016	-0.71
	TB2 - TB3	-0.26	0.31	-1.11	0.60	0.924	-0.19
	TB2 - TB4	-0.38	0.31	-1.24	0.47	0.732	-0.28
	TB3 - TB4	-0.13	0.31	-0.98	0.72	0.994	-0.09

Table B1.2 (continued)

LightScene	Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS5	TB0 - TB1	-0.69	0.31	-1.55	0.16	0.174	-0.50
	TB0 - TB2	-0.85	0.31	-1.70	0.01	0.053	-0.61
	TB0 - TB3	-1.05	0.31	-1.90	-0.20	0.007	-0.76
	TB0 - TB4	-1.15	0.31	-2.01	-0.30	0.002	-0.84
	TB1 - TB2	-0.15	0.31	-1.01	0.70	0.988	-0.11
	TB1 - TB3	-0.36	0.31	-1.21	0.49	0.780	-0.26
	TB1 - TB4	-0.46	0.31	-1.31	0.39	0.577	-0.33
	TB2 - TB3	-0.21	0.31	-1.06	0.65	0.965	-0.15
	TB2 - TB4	-0.31	0.31	-1.16	0.55	0.862	-0.22
	TB3 - TB4	-0.10	0.31	-0.96	0.75	0.997	-0.07

Table B1.3 – EMMs of GoNoGo Reaction Speed for each TB conditioned on LS.

LightScene	TestBlock	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	TB 1	2.84	0.10	2.63	3.04
	TB 2	2.80	0.10	2.59	3.00
	TB 3	2.76	0.10	2.56	2.97
LS2	TB 1	2.79	0.10	2.59	3.00
	TB 2	2.73	0.10	2.52	2.93
	TB 3	2.76	0.10	2.55	2.96
LS3	TB 1	2.73	0.10	2.52	2.93
	TB 2	2.71	0.10	2.51	2.92
	TB 3	2.65	0.10	2.45	2.86
LS4	TB 1	2.91	0.10	2.71	3.12
	TB 2	2.82	0.10	2.62	3.03
	TB 3	2.83	0.10	2.62	3.03
LS5	TB 1	2.89	0.10	2.69	3.10
	TB 2	2.83	0.10	2.62	3.04
	TB 3	2.74	0.10	2.54	2.95

Table B1.4 - Results of the contrast analysis of the GoNoGo ReactionSpeed model with an estimation of effect sizes. *df* = 540.

LightScene	Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1	TB1 - TB2	0.04	0.06	-0.08	0.16	0.531	0.14
	TB1 - TB3	0.07	0.06	-0.05	0.19	0.236	0.27
	TB2 - TB3	0.03	0.06	-0.09	0.16	0.576	0.13
LS2	TB1 - TB2	0.06	0.06	-0.06	0.18	0.310	0.23
	TB1 - TB3	0.03	0.06	-0.09	0.15	0.608	0.11
	TB2 - TB3	-0.03	0.06	-0.15	0.09	0.615	-0.11
LS3	TB1 - TB2	0.01	0.06	-0.11	0.14	0.815	0.05
	TB1 - TB3	0.07	0.06	-0.05	0.19	0.239	0.26
	TB2 - TB3	0.06	0.06	-0.06	0.18	0.345	0.21
LS4	TB1 - TB2	0.09	0.06	-0.03	0.21	0.159	0.32
	TB1 - TB3	0.08	0.06	-0.04	0.21	0.183	0.30
	TB2 - TB3	0.00	0.06	-0.13	0.12	0.940	-0.02
LS5	TB1 - TB2	0.06	0.06	-0.06	0.19	0.308	0.23
	TB1 - TB3	0.15	0.06	0.03	0.28	0.015	0.55
	TB2 - TB3	0.09	0.06	-0.03	0.21	0.155	0.32

Table B1.5 - EMMs of PVT Reaction Speed for each TB category conditioned on LS, *df* = 59.61.

LightScene	TestBlock	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	TB1	4.24	0.12	3.85	4.62
	TB2	3.99	0.12	3.60	4.37
	TB3	3.78	0.12	3.40	4.17
LS2	TB1	4.22	0.12	3.84	4.61
	TB2	3.89	0.12	3.51	4.28
	TB3	3.72	0.12	3.34	4.11
LS3	TB1	4.25	0.12	3.86	4.63
	TB2	3.98	0.12	3.59	4.36
	TB3	3.62	0.12	3.23	4.00
LS4	TB1	4.20	0.12	3.82	4.59
	TB2	3.83	0.12	3.44	4.21
	TB3	3.64	0.12	3.26	4.03
LS5	TB1	4.18	0.12	3.80	4.57
	TB2	3.85	0.12	3.47	4.24
	TB3	3.65	0.12	3.27	4.04

Table B1.6 - Results of the contrast analysis of PVT ReactionSpeed model with an estimation of effect sizes, $df = 540$.

LightScene	Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1	TB1 - TB2	0.25	0.074	0.11	0.40	0.001	0.76
	TB1 - TB3	0.46	0.074	0.31	0.60	<0.001	1.38
	TB2 - TB3	0.21	0.074	0.06	0.35	0.006	0.62
LS2	TB1 - TB2	0.33	0.074	0.19	0.48	<0.001	1.00
	TB1 - TB3	0.50	0.074	0.36	0.65	<0.001	1.52
	TB2 - TB3	0.17	0.074	0.03	0.32	0.020	0.52
LS3	TB1 - TB2	0.27	0.074	0.12	0.41	<0.001	0.80
	TB1 - TB3	0.63	0.074	0.48	0.77	<0.001	1.89
	TB2 - TB3	0.36	0.074	0.22	0.51	<0.001	1.09
LS4	TB1 - TB2	0.37	0.075	0.23	0.52	<0.001	1.13
	TB1 - TB3	0.56	0.075	0.41	0.71	<0.001	1.68
	TB2 - TB3	0.18	0.075	0.04	0.33	0.015	0.55
LS5	TB1 - TB2	0.33	0.075	0.18	0.48	<0.001	0.99
	TB1 - TB3	0.53	0.075	0.38	0.68	<0.001	1.59
	TB2 - TB3	0.20	0.075	0.05	0.35	0.008	0.60

B2 - Estimated marginal means and contrast analysis for variables of mood, visual comfort, and room comfort.

Table B2.1 - EMMs of MDFB GS scale (Gute - Schlechte Stimmung - eng.: Good – Bad mood), for each LS, df = 143.03.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	-0.575	0.626	-1.81	0.66
LS2	-1.325	0.626	-2.56	-0.09
LS3	-1.725	0.626	-2.96	-0.49
LS4	-2.344	0.632	-3.59	-1.09
LS5	-1.549	0.632	-2.80	-0.30

Table B2.2 - Results of the contrast analysis of MDFB GS model with an estimation of effect sizes, df =154.49.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	p	d
LS1 – LS2	0.75	0.74	-0.71	2.21	0.310	0.23
LS1 – LS3	1.15	0.74	-0.31	2.61	0.121	0.35
LS1 – LS4	1.77	0.74	0.30	3.24	0.018	0.54
LS1 – LS5	0.97	0.74	-0.49	2.44	0.192	0.30
LS2 – LS3	0.40	0.74	-1.06	1.86	0.588	0.12
LS2 – LS4	1.02	0.74	-0.45	2.49	0.172	0.31
LS2 – LS5	0.22	0.74	-1.24	1.69	0.764	0.07
LS3 – LS4	0.62	0.74	-0.85	2.09	0.406	0.19
LS3 – LS5	-0.18	0.74	-1.64	1.29	0.813	-0.05
LS4 – LS5	-0.79	0.75	-2.27	0.68	0.289	-0.24

Table B2.3 - EMMs of MDFB WM scale (Wachheit - Müdigkeit - eng.: Wakefulness – Fatigue), for each LS, df = 133.15.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	-5.58	1.05	-7.64	-3.51
LS2	-5.95	1.05	-8.02	-3.88
LS3	-8.08	1.05	-10.14	-6.01
LS4	-6.33	1.06	-8.42	-4.25
LS5	-5.80	1.06	-7.88	-3.71

Table B2.4 - Results of the contrast analysis of MDFB WM model with an estimation of effect sizes. *df* =154.45.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	0.37	1.19	-1.99	2.74	0.754	0.07
LS1 – LS3	2.50	1.19	0.14	4.86	0.038	0.47
LS1 – LS4	0.76	1.20	-1.62	3.14	0.529	0.14
LS1 – LS5	0.22	1.20	-2.16	2.60	0.855	0.04
LS2 – LS3	2.13	1.19	-0.24	4.49	0.077	0.40
LS2 – LS4	0.38	1.20	-1.99	2.76	0.750	0.07
LS2 – LS5	-0.15	1.20	-2.53	2.22	0.898	-0.03
LS3 – LS4	-1.74	1.20	-4.12	0.64	0.150	-0.33
LS3 – LS5	-2.28	1.20	-4.66	0.10	0.060	-0.43
LS4 – LS5	-0.54	1.21	-2.93	1.85	0.657	-0.10

Table B2.5 – EMMs of MDFB RU scale (*Ruhe-Unruhe* - eng.: *Calm – Restless*) for each LS. *df* = 138.03

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	-0.38	0.59	-1.54	0.79
LS2	-1.65	0.59	-2.81	-0.49
LS3	-1.30	0.59	-2.46	-0.14
LS4	-1.61	0.59	-2.79	-0.44
LS5	-1.66	0.59	-2.84	-0.49

Table B2.6 - Results of the contrast analysis of MDFB RU model with an estimation of effect sizes, *df* =154.47.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	1.28	0.68	-0.07	2.62	0.064	0.42
LS1 – LS3	0.93	0.68	-0.42	2.27	0.178	0.30
LS1 – LS4	1.24	0.69	-0.12	2.60	0.074	0.41
LS1 – LS5	1.29	0.69	-0.07	2.65	0.063	0.42
LS2 – LS3	-0.35	0.68	-1.70	1.00	0.609	-0.11
LS2 – LS4	-0.04	0.69	-1.40	1.32	0.957	-0.01
LS2 – LS5	0.01	0.69	-1.35	1.37	0.984	0.00
LS3 – LS4	0.31	0.69	-1.05	1.67	0.651	0.10
LS3 – LS5	0.36	0.69	-1.00	1.72	0.598	0.12
LS4 – LS5	0.05	0.69	-1.32	1.42	0.941	0.02

Table B2.7 - EMMs of Visual Comfort – Pleasantness scale for each LS, *df* = 152.96.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	3.98	0.24	3.50	4.45
LS2	3.45	0.24	2.97	3.93
LS3	3.55	0.24	3.07	4.03
LS4	3.26	0.25	2.77	3.75
LS5	3.03	0.25	2.54	3.51

Table B2.8 - Results of the contrast analysis of Visual Comfort – Pleasantness model with an estimation of effect sizes, *df* =154.54.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	0.53	0.29	-0.06	1.11	0.077	0.40
LS1 – LS3	0.43	0.29	-0.16	1.01	0.151	0.32
LS1 – LS4	0.72	0.30	0.13	1.30	0.017	0.54
LS1 – LS5	0.95	0.30	0.36	1.53	0.002	0.72
LS2 – LS3	-0.10	0.29	-0.68	0.48	0.735	-0.08
LS2 – LS4	0.19	0.30	-0.40	0.78	0.523	0.14
LS2 – LS5	0.42	0.30	-0.17	1.01	0.158	0.32
LS3 – LS4	0.29	0.30	-0.30	0.88	0.330	0.22
LS3 – LS5	0.52	0.30	-0.07	1.11	0.081	0.40
LS4 – LS5	0.23	0.30	-0.36	0.82	0.440	0.18

Table B2.9 - EMMs of Visual Comfort – Brightness scale for each LS, *df* = 149.14.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	5.20	0.15	4.90	5.50
LS2	5.33	0.15	5.03	5.62
LS3	5.55	0.15	5.25	5.85
LS4	5.49	0.15	5.19	5.79
LS5	5.82	0.15	5.52	6.13

Table B2.10 - Results of the contrast analysis Visual Comfort – Brightness model with an estimation of effect sizes. *df* =154.52.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	-0.13	0.18	-0.48	0.23	0.491	-0.15
LS1 – LS3	-0.35	0.18	-0.71	0.01	0.055	-0.43
LS1 – LS4	-0.29	0.18	-0.65	0.07	0.113	-0.36
LS1 – LS5	-0.62	0.18	-0.99	-0.26	0.001	-0.77
LS2 – LS3	-0.23	0.18	-0.58	0.13	0.216	-0.28
LS2 – LS4	-0.17	0.18	-0.53	0.19	0.364	-0.21
LS2 – LS5	-0.50	0.18	-0.86	-0.14	0.007	-0.62
LS3 – LS4	0.06	0.18	-0.30	0.42	0.749	0.07
LS3 – LS5	-0.27	0.18	-0.64	0.09	0.134	-0.34
LS4 – LS5	-0.33	0.18	-0.70	0.03	0.071	-0.41

Table B2.11 - EMMs of Visual Comfort – Glare scale for each LS, *df* = 132.83.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	3.80	0.24	3.33	4.27
LS2	4.65	0.24	4.18	5.12
LS3	4.93	0.24	4.46	5.39
LS4	5.21	0.24	4.74	5.68
LS5	5.49	0.24	5.02	5.96

Table B2.12 - Results of the contrast analysis of Visual Comfort – Glare model with an estimation of effect sizes, *df* =154.45.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	-0.85	0.27	-1.38	-0.32	0.002	-0.71
LS1 – LS3	-1.13	0.27	-1.66	-0.59	<0.001	-0.94
LS1 – LS4	-1.41	0.27	-1.94	-0.87	<0.001	-1.17
LS1 – LS5	-1.69	0.27	-2.23	-1.16	<0.001	-1.41
LS2 – LS3	-0.28	0.27	-0.81	0.26	0.308	-0.23
LS2 – LS4	-0.56	0.27	-1.09	-0.02	0.041	-0.46
LS2 – LS5	-0.84	0.27	-1.38	-0.31	0.002	-0.70
LS3 – LS4	-0.28	0.27	-0.82	0.25	0.297	-0.24
LS3 – LS5	-0.57	0.27	-1.10	-0.03	0.038	-0.47
LS4 – LS5	-0.28	0.27	-0.82	0.26	0.302	-0.23

Table B2.13 - EMMs of Visual Comfort – Color temperature acceptance scale for each LS, *df* = 100.98.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	2.93	0.17	2.59	3.26
LS2	2.95	0.17	2.61	3.29
LS3	3.03	0.17	2.69	3.36
LS4	2.95	0.17	2.61	3.29
LS5	3.15	0.17	2.82	3.49

Table B2.14 - Results of the contrast analysis of Visual Comfort – Color temperature acceptance model with an estimation of effect sizes, *df* =154.31.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	-0.03	0.17	-0.36	0.31	0.884	-0.15
LS1 – LS3	-0.10	0.17	-0.44	0.24	0.560	-0.43
LS1 – LS4	-0.02	0.17	-0.37	0.32	0.888	-0.36
LS1 – LS5	-0.23	0.17	-0.57	0.11	0.185	-0.77
LS2 – LS3	-0.08	0.17	-0.41	0.26	0.662	-0.28
LS2 – LS4	0.00	0.17	-0.34	0.34	0.997	-0.21
LS2 – LS5	-0.20	0.17	-0.55	0.14	0.238	-0.62
LS3 – LS4	0.08	0.17	-0.27	0.42	0.662	0.07
LS3 – LS5	-0.13	0.17	-0.47	0.21	0.454	-0.34
LS4 – LS5	-0.21	0.17	-0.55	0.14	0.238	-0.41

Table B2.15 - EMMs of Room Comfort – Headache scale for each LS, *df* = 102.38.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	2.93	0.17	2.59	3.26
LS2	2.95	0.17	2.61	3.29
LS3	3.03	0.17	2.69	3.36
LS4	2.95	0.17	2.61	3.29
LS5	3.15	0.17	2.82	3.49

Table B2.16 - Results of the contrast analysis of Room Comfort – Headache model with an estimation of effect sizes, $df=154.32$.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	p	d
LS1 – LS2	-0.03	0.17	-0.36	0.31	0.884	-0.15
LS1 – LS3	-0.10	0.17	-0.44	0.24	0.560	-0.43
LS1 – LS4	-0.02	0.17	-0.37	0.32	0.888	-0.36
LS1 – LS5	-0.23	0.17	-0.57	0.11	0.185	-0.77
LS2 – LS3	-0.08	0.17	-0.41	0.26	0.662	-0.28
LS2 – LS4	0.00	0.17	-0.34	0.34	0.997	-0.21
LS2 – LS5	-0.20	0.17	-0.55	0.14	0.238	-0.62
LS3 – LS4	0.08	0.17	-0.27	0.42	0.662	0.07
LS3 – LS5	-0.13	0.17	-0.47	0.21	0.454	-0.34
LS4 – LS5	-0.21	0.17	-0.55	0.14	0.238	-0.41

Table B2.17 - EMMs of Room Comfort – Perceived air quality scale for each LS, $df = 92.76$.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	5.83	0.20	5.43	6.22
LS2	5.88	0.20	5.48	6.27
LS3	5.68	0.20	5.28	6.07
LS4	5.49	0.20	5.09	5.89
LS5	5.74	0.20	5.34	6.14

Table B2.18 - Results of the contrast analysis of Room Comfort – Perceived air quality model with an estimation of effect sizes. $df=154.28$.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	p	d
LS1 – LS2	-0.05	0.20	-0.44	0.34	0.798	-0.06
LS1 – LS3	0.15	0.20	-0.24	0.54	0.444	0.17
LS1 – LS4	0.34	0.20	-0.05	0.73	0.087	0.39
LS1 – LS5	0.08	0.20	-0.31	0.47	0.673	0.10
LS2 – LS3	0.20	0.20	-0.19	0.59	0.308	0.23
LS2 – LS4	0.39	0.20	0.00	0.78	0.050	0.45
LS2 – LS5	0.13	0.20	-0.26	0.52	0.500	0.15
LS3 – LS4	0.19	0.20	-0.20	0.58	0.337	0.22
LS3 – LS5	-0.07	0.20	-0.46	0.32	0.735	-0.08
LS4 – LS5	-0.26	0.20	-0.65	0.13	0.197	-0.29

Table B2.19 - EMMs of Room Comfort – Perceived humidity scale for each LS, *df* = 182.10.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	4.05	0.09	3.88	4.22
LS2	4.10	0.09	3.93	4.27
LS3	4.05	0.09	3.88	4.22
LS4	4.05	0.09	3.88	4.23
LS5	3.90	0.09	3.72	4.07

Table B2.20 - Results of the contrast analysis of Room Comfort – Perceived humidity model with an estimation of effect sizes, *df* =154.73.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	-0.05	0.12	-0.28	0.18	0.665	-0.10
LS1 – LS3	0.00	0.12	-0.23	0.23	1.000	0.00
LS1 – LS4	0.00	0.12	-0.23	0.23	0.995	0.00
LS1 – LS5	0.15	0.12	-0.08	0.38	0.190	0.30
LS2 – LS3	0.05	0.12	-0.18	0.28	0.665	0.10
LS2 – LS4	0.05	0.12	-0.18	0.28	0.672	0.10
LS2 – LS5	0.20	0.12	-0.03	0.43	0.082	0.39
LS3 – LS4	0.00	0.12	-0.23	0.23	0.995	0.00
LS3 – LS5	0.15	0.12	-0.08	0.38	0.190	0.30
LS4 – LS5	0.15	0.12	-0.08	0.38	0.190	0.30

Table B2.21 - EMMs of Room Comfort – Perceived loudness scale for each LS, *df* = 85.42.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	2.88	0.24	2.39	3.36
LS2	3.10	0.24	2.62	3.58
LS3	2.85	0.24	2.37	3.33
LS4	3.39	0.24	2.91	3.88
LS5	3.39	0.24	2.91	3.88

Table B2.22 - Results of the contrast analysis of Room Comfort – Perceived loudness model with an estimation of effect sizes, $df = 154.24$.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	p	d
LS1 – LS2	-0.22	0.22	-0.67	0.22	0.315	-0.23
LS1 – LS3	0.03	0.22	-0.42	0.47	0.911	0.03
LS1 – LS4	-0.52	0.23	-0.96	-0.07	0.022	-0.52
LS1 – LS5	-0.52	0.23	-0.96	-0.07	0.022	-0.52
LS2 – LS3	0.25	0.22	-0.19	0.69	0.265	0.25
LS2 – LS4	-0.29	0.23	-0.74	0.15	0.193	-0.29
LS2 – LS5	-0.29	0.23	-0.74	0.15	0.193	-0.29
LS3 – LS4	-0.54	0.23	-0.99	-0.10	0.017	-0.55
LS3 – LS5	-0.54	0.23	-0.99	-0.10	0.017	-0.55
LS4 – LS5	0.00	0.23	-0.45	0.45	1.000	0.00

Table B2.23 - EMMs of Room Comfort – Perceived smell scale for each LS, $df = 110.56$.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	5.22	0.21	4.81	5.64
LS2	5.20	0.21	4.79	5.61
LS3	5.30	0.21	4.89	5.71
LS4	5.11	0.21	4.69	5.53
LS5	4.90	0.21	4.49	5.32

Table B2.24 - Results of the contrast analysis of Room Comfort – Perceived smell model with an estimation of effect sizes. $df = 154.35$.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	p	d
LS1 – LS2	0.02	0.22	-0.41	0.46	0.909	0.03
LS1 – LS3	-0.08	0.22	-0.51	0.36	0.733	-0.08
LS1 – LS4	0.12	0.22	-0.32	0.55	0.600	0.12
LS1 – LS5	0.32	0.22	-0.12	0.76	0.148	0.33
LS2 – LS3	-0.10	0.22	-0.53	0.33	0.649	-0.10
LS2 – LS4	0.09	0.22	-0.35	0.53	0.681	0.09
LS2 – LS5	0.30	0.22	-0.14	0.73	0.182	0.30
LS3 – LS4	0.19	0.22	-0.25	0.63	0.389	0.19
LS3 – LS5	0.40	0.22	-0.04	0.83	0.075	0.40
LS4 – LS5	0.21	0.22	-0.23	0.64	0.358	0.21

Table B2.25 - EMMs of Room Comfort – Perceived temperature scale for each LS, *df* = 94.17.

LightScene	EMMs	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul
LS1	3.60	0.15	3.30	3.90
LS2	3.48	0.15	3.17	3.78
LS3	3.55	0.15	3.25	3.85
LS4	3.35	0.15	3.05	3.66
LS5	3.25	0.15	2.95	3.56

Table B2.26 - Results of the contrast analysis of Room Comfort – Perceived temperature model with an estimation of effect sizes, *df* =154.29.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	CI 95% ll	CI 95% ul	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
LS1 – LS2	0.13	0.15	-0.17	0.42	0.408	0.19
LS1 – LS3	0.05	0.15	-0.25	0.35	0.740	0.07
LS1 – LS4	0.25	0.15	-0.05	0.55	0.108	0.36
LS1 – LS5	0.35	0.15	0.05	0.65	0.023	0.52
LS2 – LS3	-0.08	0.15	-0.37	0.22	0.619	-0.11
LS2 – LS4	0.12	0.15	-0.18	0.42	0.429	0.18
LS2 – LS5	0.22	0.15	-0.08	0.52	0.144	0.33
LS3 – LS4	0.20	0.15	-0.10	0.50	0.200	0.29
LS3 – LS5	0.30	0.15	0.00	0.60	0.052	0.44
LS4 – LS5	0.10	0.15	-0.20	0.40	0.503	0.15

Section C - Random effects of the fitted models

Table C1.1 - Random effects of fitted – multivariate models for cognitive performance and sleepiness variables.

Two-Factor models	$R^2_{Cond.}$	$R^2_{marg.}$	σ^2	$\tau_{00\ id}$	ICC	N_{id}	N_{obs}
Model KSS	0.43	0.10	1.90	1.11	0.37	40	990
Model GNG Speed	0.82	0.01	0.08	0.34	0.82	40	594
Model PVT Speed	0.82	0.09	0.11	0.44	0.80	40	594

Table C1.2 - Random effects of fitted univariate models for mood scales variables.

One-Factor models	$R^2_{Cond.}$	$R^2_{marg.}$	σ^2	$\tau_{00\ id}$	ICC	N_{id}	N_{obs}
Model MDFB GS	0.35	0.03	12.46	6.34	0.34	40	198
Model MDFB WM	0.36	0.02	28.55	15.14	0.35	40	198
Model MDFB RU	0.34	0.02	9.33	4.52	0.33	40	198

Table C1.3 - Random effects of fitted – univariate models for visual comfort and room comfort scales variables.

One-Factor models	$R^2_{Cond.}$	$R^2_{marg.}$	σ^2	$\tau_{00\ id}$	ICC	N_{id}	N_{obs}
Pleasantness	0.30	0.04	1.73	0.63	0.27	40	198
Brightness	0.32	0.05	0.66	0.26	0.28	40	198
Glare	0.43	0.13	1.44	0.77	0.35	40	198
Colour temperature acceptance	0.49	<0.01	0.59	0.56	0.49	40	198
Headache	0.49	<0.01	0.54	0.51	0.48	40	198
Perceived room air quality	0.53	0.01	0.76	0.84	0.52	40	198
Perceived room temperature	0.52	0.02	0.45	0.48	0.52	40	198
Perceived room humidity	0.14	0.02	0.27	0.04	0.13	40	198
Perceived room smell	0.45	0.01	0.96	0.77	0.44	40	198
Perceived room loudness	0.59	0.02	1.00	1.35	0.57	40	198

Table C1.4 - Random effects of fitted – univariate models for covariates.

One-Factor models	$R^2_{Cond.}$	$R^2_{marg.}$	σ^2	$\tau_{00\ id}$	ICC	N_{id}	N_{obs}
PSQI Score (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.32	0.40	40	594
Food Factor (KSS)	0.42	0.04	1.95	1.25	0.39	40	594
CO2 level (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.32	0.40	40	567
Humidity level (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.32	0.40	40	567
Room temp (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.33	0.40	40	567
LED LH (KSS)	0.42	0.02	1.94	1.34	0.41	40	594
Indoor DL LH (KSS)	0.40	<0.01	1.97	1.33	0.40	40	594
Time outside (KSS)	0.42	<0.01	1.95	1.39	0.42	40	594
PSQI Score (GNG Speed)	0.81	<0.01	0.08	0.34	0.81	40	594
Food Factor (GNG Speed)	0.83	0.02	0.08	0.38	0.83	40	594
CO2 level (GNG Speed)	0.82	<0.01	0.08	0.35	0.82	40	567
Humidity level (GNG Speed)	0.83	<0.01	0.07	0.35	0.82	40	567
Room temp (GNG Speed)	0.82	<0.01	0.08	0.35	0.82	40	567
LED LH (GNG Speed)	0.81	<0.01	0.08	0.34	0.81	40	594
Indoor DL LH (GNG Speed)	0.81	<0.01	0.08	0.34	0.81	40	594
Time outside (GNG Speed)	0.81	<0.01	0.08	0.33	0.81	40	594
PSQI Score (PVT Speed)	0.73	0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	594
Food Factor (PVT Speed)	0.74	0.01	0.16	0.46	0.74	40	594
CO2 level (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	567
Humidity level (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	567
Room temp (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	567
LED LH (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	594
Indoor DL LH (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	594
Time outside (PVT Speed)	0.73	0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	594

Table C1.5 - Random effects of fitted – univariate models for covariates.

<i>One-Factor models – VC Covariate</i>	$R^2_{Cond.}$	$R^2_{marg.}$	σ^2	$\tau_{00\ id}$	<i>ICC</i>	N_{id}	N_{obs}
Glare (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.32	0.40	40	594
Pleasantness (KSS)	0.42	0.04	1.95	1.25	0.39	40	594
Brightness (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.32	0.40	40	567
CCT acceptance (KSS)	0.40	<0.00	1.97	1.32	0.40	40	567
Glare (GnG Speed)	0.81	<0.01	0.08	0.34	0.81	40	594
Pleasantness (GnG Speed)	0.83	0.02	0.08	0.38	0.83	40	594
Brightness (GnG Speed)	0.82	<0.01	0.08	0.35	0.82	40	567
CCT acceptance (GnG Speed)	0.83	<0.01	0.07	0.35	0.82	40	567
Glare (PVT Speed)	0.73	0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	594
Pleasantness (PVT Speed)	0.74	0.01	0.16	0.46	0.74	40	594
Brightness (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	567
CCT acceptance (PVT Speed)	0.73	<0.01	0.16	0.43	0.73	40	567